

Effect of pesticide on human health and environment maternal and child health issues in agricultural areas in Brebes: Impact of pesticide use?*Suhartono***Environmental Health Department, Public Health Faculty, Diponegoro University***Corresponding author: _damas@yahoo.com***INTRODUCTION**

Brebes Regency located in the North Coast of Java Island (*Pantai Utara Jawa*, Pantura) is the highest shallots production region in Indonesia. Shallots are susceptible to pests like insects and fungi. Therefore, nearly all of the farmers in this area mix various types of pesticides and exceed the recommended dose as shown in a pesticide label. Data obtained from the Brebes Agriculture Office demonstrated that the level of pesticide use in Brebes Regency was the largest both in Indonesia and in Southeast Asia. There are approximately 3,200 pesticide brands registered by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia in which about 1,300 of these brands are distributed in Brebes Regency (Agriculture Office of Brebes Regency, 2017). Our studies conducted in several villages in Brebes Regency showed that farmers in these areas mixed 2-3 types of pesticides before spraying shallots with a frequency of spraying about 2-4 times a week in dry season and every day in rainy season (Suhartono et al, 2012). Amount of pesticide use by shallot farmers in Brebes Regency was 330,000 liters per planting season in which they had four planting seasons a year (Agriculture Office of Brebes Regency, 2017).

Some health problems, specifically related to Maternal and Child Health (MCH), were widely found in Brebes Regency. Data from the Central Java Province Health Office in 2016 showed that maternal mortality cases in Brebes Regency were the highest in Central Java Province, reaching 54 cases. Meanwhile, infant mortality rates (13.42 per 1000 live births) placed the seventh of 37 regencies/cities in Central Java (WHO, 2017). The incidence of stunting in children in Brebes Regency was also relatively high, reaching 40.7% (Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia, 2013). Stunting (height for age < -2 SD of the WHO Child Growth Standards median), referred to as failure of linear growth is a strong marker of unhealthy growth given its association with morbidity and mortality risk, non-communicable diseases in later life, and learning capacity and productivity. It is also closely linked with child development in several domains including cognitive, language and sensory-motor capacities (WHO, 2014).

The maternal mortality, infant mortality and stunting, are health problems that often occur in the first 1000 days of life (from the beginning of the

fetus to two years old children). Health problems in the first 1000 days of life really need our attention together, because this phase is a golden period of human life that will determine the quality of the nation in the future. So far, efforts to overcome this problems have focused in the aspect of nutrition⁵, because of the very strong relationship between nutrition and health and growth⁶. The possible role of exposure to toxic substances in the environment like pesticide as one of the main 'causes' of maternal and child health problems also needs our attention. It is very potential as a risk factor for maternal and child health problems in agricultural areas. Even though it is not easy to ensure that the high level of pesticide use is a main cause of various maternal and child health problems in Brebes Regency, some findings from previous studies supported by related theories demonstrated the harmful effects of pesticides on maternal and child health.

Research Results and Theories on the Impact of Pesticides on Maternal and Child Health

Theories and many previous studies on the effects of pesticides on human health have been widely published but efforts to overcome this problem have not been carried out optimally. The results of our studies regarding the adverse effects of pesticides specifically on maternal and child health that had been conducted in Brebes Regency and supported by theories and the results of research abroad are presented in this paper.

Impact of Pesticides on the Thyroid Functions

Some types of pesticides that are often used in the shallot farming area of Brebes include Mancozeb, Dithane, and Chlorpyrifos (Budiono, 2018). These pesticides are classified as endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), chemical compounds in the environment that can interfere with the biosynthesis, metabolism, and hormone function in the body and can affect hormone balance function (homeostasis) and reproduction (Diamanti-Kandarakis et al, 2009; Mnif et al, 2011). A thyroid hormone is one of the hormone types that can be disrupted by exposure to EDCs (Calsolaro et al, 2017; Miller et al 2009). The hormone is indispensable in the process of metabolism and human growth (Mullur et al, 2013; Brent, 2000). A previous study conducted in an agricultural area in a sub district of Brebes Regency in 2010 demonstrated that the prevalence of hypothyroidism among women of childbearing age reached 22.2% (Suhartono, 2010), higher than other cities in Indonesia like Jakarta, Bandung, Semarang, Surabaya and Malang that was only 0.5% (Abbot Laboratories Diagnostic Division, 2008). Some studies conducted internationally showed that

the prevalence of hypothyroidism in women group ranging from 0.3% to 2.9% (Vanderpump, 2011).

Our study also proves, that pesticide exposure is a risk factor for the incidence of hypothyroidism in women of childbearing age (Suhartono, 2012) and in children (Budiyono, 2018). Women with a history of exposure to pesticides are at risk three times to suffer from hypothyroidism (Suhartono, 2012). Hypothyroidism is a condition in which the body lacks thyroid hormone which is characterized by increased levels of thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) and a decrease in T4 (ATA, 2013). A study in Brazil showed a link between pesticide exposure in the workplace and the incidence of thyroid dysfunction (hypothyroid-like effects), especially in men (Piccoli et al, 2016). Research in Iowa and North Carolina (United States) demonstrated that exposure to chlordane insecticides, benomyl and mancozeb fungicides, and paraquat herbicides were risk factors for the incidence of hypothyroidism in women in agricultural areas (Goldner, 2010). Benomyl and mancozeb, which are also widely used in the agricultural area of Brebes district, are both fungicides with carbamate groups. The dithiocarbamate pesticides ethylenebisdithiocarbamate and ethylenethiourea have been associated with thyroid dysfunction. Maneb/mancozeb has been shown to cause hypothyroidism in rabbits (Malle et al, 2006), and human workers exposed to ethylenethiourea showed significantly lower levels of total T4 compared with unexposed controls (Smith, 1984). In another study of unprotected workers heavily exposed to ethylenebisdithiocarbamate, TSH levels were elevated, but T4 levels were no different from those of controls (Steeland et al, 1997).

Normal thyroid function in pregnant women is very important because it will determine the quality of the child it contains (Lazarus, 2011). Women with hypothyroidism have decreased fertility; even if they conceive, risk of abortion is increased, and risk of gestational hypertension, anemia, placentaabruption and postpartum hemorrhage are increased (Abalovich et al, 2002). Severe hypothyroidism has been associated with pre-eclampsia, placental abnormalities, low birth weight infants, and postpartum hemorrhage (bleeding)(ATA, 2014). A cohort study in the Netherlands proved that maternal hypothyroxinaemia during early gestation was an independent determinant of a delay in infant neurodevelopment. However, when the thyroxin (fT4) concentrations increase during pregnancy in women who are hypothyroxinaemic during early gestation, infant development appears not to be adversely affected (Pop et al, 2003).

In Brebes Regency, women and children living in agricultural areas are generally involved in various agricultural activities, such as finding pests and removing shallots from their stalks (*mrotoli*) after harvesting. These activities are very risky to expose to pesticides because few days prior harvesting, shallot

farmers spray their shallot plants. Application of pesticides to crops may leave residue on plants. Exposure to pesticides in humans can occur through several routes, namely the respiratory tract (inhalation), direct contact with the skin or through the gastrointestinal tract (by oral) (Kalayanova & El Bataw, 1991). The involvement of women and children in agricultural activities increases the risk of exposure to pesticides, especially exposure through direct contact with the skin. The '*mrotoli*' activity is usually carried out by them without using personal protective equipment like masks or gloves to prevent pesticide residues in shallot plants entering their bodies through respiratory air or skin pores. Pesticide contamination in the environment (water, soil and food) also increases the risk of indirect exposure. A study conducted by the Health Ministry's Health Research and Development Agency of the Republic of Indonesia in several agricultural areas in Brebes Regency demonstrated that five of 12 rivers or 42% were positively contaminated with organophosphate pesticides residue (Badan Litbang Kemenkes RI, 2014). In addition, the Indonesian Agricultural Environment Research Institute reported that chlorpyrifos pesticide residues were found in four of the five shallot samples examined (Balai penelitian lingkungan pertanian, 2018).

Our study in Brebes showed that pesticide exposure is a risk factor for sub-clinical hypothyroidism (SCH) in school children living in an agricultural areas (Suhartono et al, 2018). SCH or mild hypothyroidism is characterized by mildly elevated serum TSH concentrations, with normal concentrations of serum free and total triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4), without the typical symptoms of thyroid disease (Biondi & Cooper, 2008). The abnormalities most frequently associated in the pediatric population are goiter, poor school performance, weight gain, increased cholesterol levels, impaired growth velocity, anemia, excessive sleepiness, weakness, and impaired psychomotor and cognitive development (Wu et al, 2006; Aijaz et al, 2006). Another study in Brebes Regency concluded that the proportion of goiter in the children whose fathers were farmer (80.8%) were higher than those whose fathers non-farmers (43.2%) (Kartini et al, 2018).

The impact of pesticides on maternal health (pregnancy)

The high maternal mortality rate in Brebes Regency might be related to the high use of pesticides in the area. Data from the Brebes Regency Health Office showed that the main cause of maternal mortality in Brebes was pre-eclampsia (PE), which was 32% (Brebes District Health Office 2016). PE is an increase in blood pressure (gestational hypertension) and proteinuria at over 20 weeks of pregnancy (The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2013). Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy are an important cause of severe

morbidity, long-term disability and death among both mothers and their babies. In Africa and Asia, nearly one tenth of all maternal deaths are associated with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, whereas one quarter of maternal deaths in Latin America have been associated with those complications (WHO, 2011). Several studies have shown that pesticide exposure increases the risk of hypertension in pregnant women (Saldana et al, 2009; Ledda et al, 2015). These studies suggest that the risk of both Pregnancy Induced Hypertension (PIH) and PE was elevated among women who performed activities likely to have exposed them to pesticides during their first trimester of pregnancy (Saldana et al, 2009). A previous study reported of an association between pesticide exposure and gestational diabetes (Saldana et al, 2007). Diabetes caused endothelial dysfunction (Dandona et al, 2006), which may contribute to the pathophysiology of PE (Lyell et al, 2003), as supported by studies showing that tight glycemic control reduces the risk of PE in women who had diabetes before becoming pregnant (Crowther et al, 2005; Fan et al, 2006). Pesticide exposure in pregnant women is also suspected of causing fetal growth disorder and increase the risk of low birth weight. A study in Brazilian rural areas demonstrated that the per capita pesticide sales were directly associated with higher prevalence of children born with low birth weight ($r = 0.403$), with birth weights between 1500 and 2500 grams ($r = 0.366$), and very low birth weight birth ($r = 0.476$). All correlations were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) (Boccolini et al, 2013).

In addition to pesticides, other toxic substances that could increase the risk of PE was lead (plumbum, Pb) (Bayat et al, 2016; Jameil, 2016; Poropat et al, 2018). Ikechukwu et al. (2012) stated that lead increases the circulating levels of endothelin. Endothelin is a vasoactive that constricts the diameter of blood vessels thereby affecting blood pressure. Lead also reduces serum levels of vasodilator substances such as nitric oxide (NO) and endothelial-derived relaxation factor (EDRF) due to a lead-mediated increase in reactive oxygen species (Carmignani et al, 2000; Gonick & Behari, 2002). Lead inhibits membrane adenosine triphosphatases (ATPases), which increases intracellular calcium ions and vasoconstriction (Moreau et al, 1988). Mechanisms cause preeclampsia either by inducing vasoconstriction and placental ischemia or direct toxicity on the endothelial cell and the renal function and thus causing proteinuria, which is a common feature of preeclampsia (Ikechukwu et al, 2012).

The results of our study in six Puskesmas areas on the northern coast of Brebes Regency showed that almost all pregnant women (98%) had blood Pb levels above $10 \mu / \text{dL}$ (Suhartono et al, 2017), while the CDC threshold value was $5 \mu \text{g} / \text{dL}$ (Ettinger & Wengrovitz, 2010). This study also proved pregnant women with high blood Pb levels were two times more likely to develop hypertension (gestational hypertension) than those with low blood Pb levels (Suhartono et al, 2017). Some types of pesticides used in Brebes Regency that

contain lead were Antracol 70 WP, Buldok 25 EC dan Dithane M-45, Mancozeb and Profenofos (Hartini, 2010).

The impact of pesticides on children's growth and development

Young children are particularly vulnerable to toxicants in the environment, including pesticides (Liu & Schelar, 2012). Children's organs are not fully developed until later in life. They continually experience critical periods in development; adverse exposures can cause permanent damage, particularly in utero (Chalupka & Chalupka, 2010). Children's behaviors and ability to interact with their physical environment change during different stages of growth and development and can place them at greater risk of exposure: children may crawl on the floor, explore objects orally, and play with items they find in the environment (Landrigan, 2004). For their weight, children consume more food and drink than adults, increasing their possible dietary exposure; dietary exposure is compounded by children's immature livers and excretory systems, which may be unable to effectively remove pesticide metabolites (Landrigan, 2004). These metabolites may block the absorption of critical nutrients in children's diets, which further affects health outcomes. Potential routes of exposure to pesticides include in utero or through breast milk, via ingestion of food contaminated with pesticides, and household exposures via dermal contact (Chalupka & Chalupka, 2010). Children live closer to the ground than adults, which may increase their exposure to pesticides sprayed or precipitated there (Paulson & Barnett, 2010).

Research in 2014 in the Brebes agricultural area showed more than 30% of primary school-aged children were detected dialkyl phosphates (DAPs), metabolites of multiple organophosphorus pesticides, in their urine. Meanwhile, the results of X-ray examination proved that 27 of the 50 children (54.0%) were delay in skeletal maturation (bone-age delay) (Kartini et al, 2016). Another study by Kartini et alin 2017 proved that pesticide exposure was a risk factor for stuntingamong primary school-aged children in Brebes agricultural areas, children with a history of exposure to pesticides were 4.5 times risk of suffering from stunting than those without exposure (Kartini, 2017).

Exposure to toxic substances in the environment, including pesticides, leads to oxidative stress (Lukaszewicz-hussain, 2010) which led to an increase in the use of energy for the activation of the immune system, thereby reducing the use of energy for the maintenance, reproduction, growth and thermoregulation (Degen, 2006). Exposure to pesticides can also interfere with the function of several growth hormones, such as IGF-1 hormone which is very necessary in the process of child growth (Boada et al, 2007). Recent research suggests that even low levels of pesticide exposure can affect young children's neurological and behavioral development. Evidence shows a link between pesticides and

neonatal reflexes, psychomotor and mental development, and attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). In utero dialkyl phosphate (DAPs), the organophosphate metabolites, and, to a lesser extent, postnatal DAPs were associated adversely with attention as assessed by maternal report, psychometrician observation, and direct assessment. These associations were stronger at 5 years than at 3.5 years and were stronger in boys (Marks et al, 2010). A study in USA showed an adverse associations of prenatal DAPs with mental development and pervasive developmental problems at 24 months of age (Eskenazi et al, 2007). Another research concluded that organophosphate exposure might be associated with deficits in learning on neurobehavioral performance, particularly in tests of with motor function (Butler-Dawson et al, 2016). A study in the USA showed that children who were detected organophosphate pesticide metabolites in their urine were at risk of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), a developmental disorder characterized by concentration difficulties and hyperactive behavior (Marks et al, 2010; Yu et al, 2016). Children with levels higher than the median of detectable concentrations had double the odds of ADHD (adjusted OR, 1.93 [95% CI, 1.23–3.02]) compared with those with non-detectable levels (Bouchard et al, 2010).

Lead commonly contained in pesticides has been primarily classified as a neurotoxin (Lanphear et al, 2005; Lidsky & Schneider, 2003) and is associated with developmental and behavioral problems in children (WHO, 2010; Lewendon et al, 2001; Gould, 2009). Preventing lead exposure in infants and young children is important because lead can affect their developing brain and nervous system. High levels of lead can adversely affect the nervous system and kidneys of adults and children Wisconsin Department of Health Services, 2010). A study in Bangladesh concluded that chronic lead poisoning is significantly associated with high level of stunting among child slum dwellers (Raihan et al, 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

People living in agricultural areas are at risk of being exposed to various toxic substances, such as pesticides and heavy metals like lead (Pb) which are contained in many pesticides. Exposure can occur directly, through their involvement in agricultural activities, or indirectly through contact with the environment contaminated by pesticide residues in water, air, soil, agricultural or food products. Exposure to pesticides and lead was a risk factor for various types of health problems specifically related to hormonal dysfunction and the quality of fetal or child growth and development. In Indonesia, distribution and the use of pesticide needs to be well regulated in order to prevent adverse health effects due to pesticide exposure in the future.

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